

Abdurauf Fitrat's Views on the Issues of State Independence

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ABSTRACT

This article is dedicated to the views of the Uzbek historian, philologist, translator, writer, playwright and poet, one of the founders of the modern Uzbek language and literature, Abdurauf Fitrat, on the independence of the state.

Keywords: History; Session; Independence; State; Nation; Development; Jadidism; Union; Law.

1. Introduction

Uzbekistan's state independence has created great conditions for the development of social-economic, political-legal spheres. At the same time, it opened completely new pages in our spiritual and cultural life. The sense of pride in the rich historical memory, spiritual and cultural heritage leads to a deep understanding of the nation's identity. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted the following: "The scientific-educational and literary-artistic legacy of those who sacrificed their lives for the freedom of our country and the happiness of our people is still of inestimable importance for us today" [1].

2. Discussion

It should be said that many progressive intellectuals, self-sacrificing young people who were unfair victims of the period of repression have set themselves the goal of development of the nation and the country, development of science and enlightenment. At the same time, they also aimed to implement major political changes and gain independence. Political independence of the nation and the people is stipulated in their works and programs. In particular, the provisions on the independence of the country and the nation are expressed in the 9-point program of the modern "Erk" party.

Article 3 of the program contains the following points: "Turkestan will be saved from the hands of the colonialists and independent administration will be achieved. This creates conditions for the growth of class stratification in the country and allows the peasants to develop to the point where they can defend their rights" [2; 110]. The total abolition of the colonial system and colonialism, as well as the independence of Turkestan, were not only an idea for the Jadids but also their practical activities.

Enlightenment thinker Abdurauf Fitrat wrote: If the disunity and disunity prevailing among the members of the society is ended, the desired goal can be achieved if all the peoples of Turkestan unite as one body and soul against the colonialists. Efforts of unity and transparency have reached the level of necessity. However, unity is a difficult issue. Action without unity is also extremely harmful [3; 134].

Fitrat strongly criticized the society in which he lived and the social-political disorder established in it. Abdurauf Fitrat brutally exposes the barbaric nature of the colonial policy of the Russian Empire: "... we were oppressed,

humiliated, our hands were tied, our mouths were tied, our land was taken. In addition, our property was looted, our honor was damaged, our honor was disrespected, our rights were violated, and our humanity was trampled underfoot. Our people have been patient with all this” [4].

Also, Abdurauf Fitrat was sentenced to brutal torture by the Russian Empire, its representatives in Turkestan and local officials. Nevertheless, Fitrat calls on all indigenous workers of Turkestan, whose dignity, will and rights have been violated, to fight for national freedom and independence.

This is what Abdurauf Fitrat wrote in his work “Autonomy”: First of all, a strong army is needed to protect an independent state from internal and external threats. A national army headed by a single command must stand with the people. It ensures the peace of the country and the peace of citizens and the military forces relying on the public are the strength of the state. Therefore, the national army should rely on the support of the nation. “power is necessary to maintain autonomy” [4]. Abdurauf Fitrat emphasizes the need for Turkestan Autonomy as a new form of state to take care of the people, organize a strong defense and ensure the independence of the state.

According to Fitrat, the establishment of a national independent democratic state, the establishment of peace and justice in the country will lead to the strengthening of people’s power and the establishment of new political orders in society that are in the interest of citizens. At the same time, Abdurauf Fitrat commented on the fact that Autonomy, as a national democratic state, is on a higher level than the Turkestan General-Governorship. According to Fitrat, during the General-Governorship in Turkestan, citizens were deprived not only of their political rights, but also of their right to free thought: “We did not give thought to every command based on force, we kept it in our faith...” [4]. Abdurauf Fitrat said that the citizen “when he returned crying from the courthouse doors, while lying in dark prisons, when he fell with the reaction of cruel soldiers” protested that human dignity and rights have fallen to the ground [4]. Fitrat tries to explain the essence to the people at a time when lawlessness reigns in society “when our homes are burned, when our fellow believers are hanged” [4].

Fitrat shows that citizens’ rights and self-determination cannot be achieved by the declaration of autonomy. Commenting on the fact that the new state form - Turkestan Autonomy is still relative, believes that it is necessary to preserve, strengthen and ensure its stability. Also, Fitrat, expressing an opinion that the people of Turkestan are oppressed by double oppression, shows that the reason for this is national and colonial oppression in the country. According to him, the rights of Turkestans in courts, houses, roads, commercial affairs, even in carriages were kept lower than those of Russians and Armenians who were foreigners of Turkestan [6].

Fitrat said that as a result of the establishment of colonial rules in the society, the condition of the local people has worsened. At the same time, human rights were severely violated and the population was oppressed under double oppression. The policies of the colonial authorities, consisting of destruction, extermination, and looting in the country, brought countless hardships to the local people.

3. Results

According to Abdurauf Fitrat, our people returned helpless from state courts. Suffered the terrible torment of prisons. Human rights were violated by the colonialists. Compatriots were hanged. After these events, our minds was lost, our brains were corrupted, our eyes were blind, and we literally cannot see anything [4].

It should be noted that Abdurauf Fitrat and his fellow progressive intellectuals understood very well that disunity and disunity are a serious obstacle in the struggle for national liberation and independence.

Fitrat always tried to convey the following in his views: For all nations and communities, there is no greater crisis than separation and disunity. The first reason for the disappearance of people whose names have remained in history is disunity and disunity. Calling upon the people to fight for independence and freedom, he calls upon his compatriots for mutual unity and cooperation: “O Muslims of Turkestan! for Allah, for the prophet, for religion, let’s unite for the nation. Let’s get away from personal conflicts and class divisions among us; let us be bound by the threads of brotherhood and union, which are the first commandments of Islam; Let us all gather together for the sake of God, religion, country, and nation. Let’s help and help each other” [7].

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, the efforts of the great enlightened thinker Abdurauf Fitrat, who lived as my people and my country, to unite the people towards great national goals are commendable. Abdurauf Fitrat on mutual unity and cooperation, alliance and union to achieve independence and freedom, state independence, advanced ideas on the issues of establishing a national democratic state are of great importance in strengthening the state independence of Uzbekistan at the present time. At the same time, it is important to realize the noble goal of building a legal state.

Limitations

The real genotype data was infeasible due to the lack of funding. In addition, there is insufficient laboratory support for handling huge amount of sequencing data that could be obtained from few accessible data repository website.

Declarations

Source of Funding

The study has not received any funds from any organization.

Competing Interests Statement

The author has declared no competing interests.

Consent for Publication

The author declares that she consented to the publication of this study.

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